

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

D5.6 – Delivery Mechanisms for Personalised Healthcare and Real-Time Feedback I

WP5 AI for Early Risk Assessment and Personalised
Recommendations

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Executive summary

The objective of this deliverable is to report on the developments regarding the delivery mechanisms for personalised healthcare and real-time feedback in the first phase of the iHelp project. This is the first version of a series of deliverables of this task, which seeks to deliver the user-centric smart application to support the delivery of personalized healthcare through the use of mobile, IoT and wearable technologies. To this end, this deliverable provides information on the user centric application through which the personalised healthcare solutions are delivered. It also describes the design and implementation of the software interfaces and personalised engagement strategies that will be used to deliver the personalised recommendations and gather feedback. Ultimately, this report accompanies the software that has been developed as part of the T5.3 (“Delivery Mechanisms for Personalised Healthcare and Real-time Feedback”) until M16 of the iHelp project. An updated and final version of this document will be released on M32.

1 Introduction

As stated as the official objective, this deliverable D5.6 aims to describe the different user centric applications developed in the iHelp project to deliver the personalised healthcare solutions. The use of mobile, IoT and wearable technologies is elaborated as well as the design of personalised engagement strategies and software interfaces that are used to deliver the personalised recommendations and gather feedback.

This deliverable is the first document, describing the initial results achieved in the context of T5.3 (“Delivery Mechanisms for Personalised Healthcare and Real-time Feedback”). The official task description reads as follows:

*This task **delivers the user-centric smart applications to support the delivery of personalized healthcare through the use of mobile, IoT and wearable technologies.** Various scenarios and deployment configurations will be realized and validated, targeting different prevention and interventions measures, prediction of the risks and auditing of the identified risks against the targeted recommendations for personalised health support. The targeted **recommendations (prevention/interventions measures) provided by the user-centric applications will be based on the models developed in T4.2, and the other tasks in this work package** and could range from adherence (e.g. reminders) to support of daily activities. Moreover, the emotion AI outcomes (Task 5.4) will be used to enhance the real-time recommendations and adapt them in real-time according to the emotional/social/societal behaviours of the users. Thus, the virtual assistant will not be limited to giving standardized health advice to patients, rather it will be based on continuous analysis of patient’s behaviour and current state, in order to tailor feedback on the individual situation. In summary, this task focuses on providing the mechanisms for delivering personalised healthcare and real-time feedback, by means of (a) **data visualisation tools**, (b) **messages and reminders**, and (c) **conversational coaching**.*

Below in Section 1.1 we describe how, given the overall objective of this task, the delivery of personalised healthcare fits within the bigger picture of the iHelp platform, and the project as a whole. Then in Section 1.2 we see how the work described here is linked to the work performed in other Work Packages and Tasks within the project, and finally in Section 1.3 we lay out and explain the structure of this document.

1.1 Delivery Mechanisms in the Bigger Picture

In a previous deliverable on state-of-the-art and requirements analysis (A., C., C. + 21), we distinguished three categories of common types of delivery mechanisms in our analysis. These were the following:

- Data visualisation
- Feedback messages and nudges
- Conversational coaching

We have structured this deliverable following those three main categories and also include this structure in our discussion of the background technology. The delivery mechanisms for personalised healthcare and real-time feedback provide the communication between platform and end-user. Within the iHelp project, these delivery mechanisms are embedded in the Healthentia mobile app – on which we will elaborate further in Section 2. In the app, end-users can register and be assigned to various “Study” configurations, which then determine the availability of various features (e.g., specific widgets). This is of interest when it

comes to delivery mechanisms, since these are features that can be adjusted to the needs of each of the five pilots and/or to specific end-users.

As stated, the delivery mechanisms will provide the communication between the platform and end-users. This means that they can be used to retrieve additional end-user data for the Holistic Health Records, can be used to communicate personalised recommendations and care plans - or the executive elements of those -, can be used to communicate the results of monitoring, alerting, risk assessment and evaluation of personalised recommendations, and of course to provide virtual coaching. These are especially relevant for the iHelp objectives on effective and efficient recommendations (Objective 3), user-engagement and personalised interfaces (Objective 4), and to some extent also to providing a holistic view of individualised data (Objective 5).

Objective 3: *Design of effective and efficient recommendations (based on targeted prevention and intervention models for Pancreatic Cancer) that can be delivered to (high risk) individuals through Internet of Things, mobile apps and wearable technologies.*

Objective 4: *Development of user-engagement toolset and personalised interfaces to support delivery (and capturing feedback) of early risk identification, prevention and intervention mechanisms.”*

Objective 5: *Development of Holistic Health Records (HHRs) as a standardised base for data modelling and management; to provide a holistic view of individualised data obtained from medical (primary) as well as from lifestyle, behavioural and social (secondary) aspects.*

Looking at the overall picture of the iHelp platform and technology, we refer to Figure 1 below that shows the high-level component overview of the platform. In this image, there are two components that make up the work described in this document and task. On the one hand there is the “iHelp for Individual” block in the top left corner of the image, depicting the mobile phone and all the interactions with end-users. Second, in the back-end, there is the Personalised Advisor component (inside the “Additional Features” block) that depicts the back-end processing activities needed to deliver e.g. virtual coaching to the mobile application.

Arch_v1.0.6

Figure 1: High level component architecture view as taken from iHelp D2.5.

1.2 Interactions with other tasks

Within work package 5, the work discussed in this deliverable in particular builds on and relates to the following tasks and deliverables:

- WP2, T2.1, D2.3: State of the art and requirements analysis III. This deliverable’s Section 4.11 provides a background on delivery mechanisms and defines user requirements for delivery mechanisms.
- WP5, T5.2, D5.4: Design of personalised prevention and intervention measures I. This deliverable describes the design of the content that will be delivered through the delivery mechanisms.

Furthermore, this task builds upon the input from T5.2 (“Design of Personalised Prevention and Intervention Measures”), T5.5 (“Monitoring, Alerting, Feedback and Evaluation Mechanisms”), T2.4 (“User Centered Design”), and WP6 related to the pilots and the use cases of the project.

1.3 Structure of this document

The rest of this document is structured as follows. First in Section 2 we describe the background technology (Healthentia) on which the iHelp specific software is being built. Then in Section 3 we describe

the “Data Visualisation” activities that take place in the context of this task – under this umbrella term we also include any modifications needed for the mobile application that cannot be considered under the next section. Section 4 constitutes the core of this deliverable and focuses on Virtual Coaching – the core mechanism of delivering feedback and personalized coaching to users in the iHelp platform. Finally, in Section 5 we describe the work-in-progress Clinical Pathway Tool that can be used by healthcare professionals to control the high-level composition of a study or digital therapy.

2 Background technology

The delivery mechanisms for personalised healthcare and real-time feedback are incorporated in the Healthentia platform and users will interact with them using the Healthentia Mobile app. In this section we therefore describe the functionalities of the Healthentia Mobile app as a baseline, while highlighting the features that will be (further) developed in the context of the iHelp project.

Healthentia is an eClinical platform for capturing, processing, and reporting Real World Data (RWD) and derived analytics. It has a back-end that supports management and processing of data, a web portal on which data analytics and data entry can be visualized and mobile apps for RWD data capturing (both for iOS and Android). Over the course of the iHelp project, the user interface for the Mobile app has already been significantly transformed (see Figure 2 for a before and after).

Figure 2: Screenshots of the older (left) and newer (right) interfaces for the Healthentia Mobile app.

Previously, we identified three types of categories of delivery mechanisms, namely: data visualisation, feedback messages and nudges, and virtual coaching (previously conversational coaching). We will use these to structure our discussion of the Healthentia Mobile app.

2.1 Data visualisation

At the time of writing, the Healthentia Mobile app contains the following widgets:

e-Diary

The e-Diary provides the user with a history of all their interactions with the study in the Healthentia mobile app. These include, for example, completed questionnaires or questionnaires that are still open to answer. When one of the complete questionnaires is selected the user can see a log of their responses.

Vital signs (blood pressure, oximeter, heart rate)

This group of widgets lets users track their blood pressure, oxygen saturation levels and heart rate. While the heart rate is synchronised from a wearable device, the blood pressure and oxygen saturation levels can be synchronised or logged manually.

Activity

Healthentia can be connected to a number of activity tracking devices (within iHelp the connection with Fitbit and Garmin will be used within the different pilots) or the user can use their phone by connecting with Apple Health or Google Health.

Sleep

Sleep data are automatically collected through the integrated activity trackers. Additionally, users can log their sleep by adding a start time and date and end time and date.

Liquid consumption

Users can log their liquid consumption, which includes the amount, and type of liquid.

Weight

The user can synchronise weight measurements from a device or log them manually.

Medication management

The medication management widget lets users log when they should take their medication, and if and when they would like to receive reminders for this. Once medication is added to the log (this can be done once with a repeating pattern), users can indicate per day and added type of medication that they have taken their medication.

Teleconsultation and chatting

Finally, the teleconsultation and chatting widget allows the user to send a message to the person conducting the study. This makes this widget slightly different from the other widgets in the sense that it is not a means to input a specific type of data.

Nutrition widget (under development)

To provide users with more insight into their health status as well as to allow them to input data in the iHelp project a nutrition widget will be added – the design of which is described in more detail in Section 3.3.

We will elaborate more on the data visualisation for the data collection widgets (i.e., not the teleconsultation and chatting) in Section 3.

2.2 Feedback messages and nudges

The Healthentia mobile app can give notifications such as ‘a new questionnaire is available’. As discussed in the previous state-of-the-art analysis, valuable features when it comes to personalised healthcare and

real-time feedback are the inclusion of feedback messages and nudges, not only pertaining to the collection of data, but also when it comes to virtual coaching.

In addition to notifications that will nudge users to fill in questionnaires, the notification feature in the mobile app could be used to present a user with a coaching message or a message that states that the coach in the app would like to talk to them. We do not specifically discuss this in this deliverable, as these messages can be seen as an extension to or part of the virtual coaching.

2.3 Virtual coaching

At the start of the iHelp project the Healthentia Mobile app contained a simple chatbot that provided some basic dialogues. Such conversational interaction can be leveraged to provide virtual coaching. This feature of the app therefore is being extended to facilitate more intelligent interactions. This is the subject of Section 4 in this deliverable.

3 Data visualisation

In the following subsections, we provide information on the support for iHelp branding in the Healthentia mobile app and we shortly describe the visualisation of collected data in that mobile app.

3.1 Support for iHelp Branding

The Healthentia Mobile app will be adjusted to feature the iHelp colours and logo. Figure 3 below shows an example of the default version of the mobile app, and Figure 4 shows what the app will look like with iHelp branding.

Figure 3: A screenshot showing an example of the default Healthentia Mobile app branding.

Figure 4: The Healthentia mobile app with iHelp branding.

3.2 Data visualisation in the Healthentia Mobile app

Each of the widgets in the Healthentia mobile app provides the user with some visualisation of their data. The figures below show an example of what the visualisation of the widgets on the main screen looks like, and what this looks like when a specific widget is opened (in this case the liquids widget). Note that every study can be configured to either include or exclude widgets – depending on the needs of the study.

Figure 5: A screenshot showing an overview of the widgets on the main page in the app.

Figure 6: Data visualization for the liquids widget.

3.3 Nutrition Widget

The nutrition widget will be one of the widgets that can be turned on for participants in the Healthentia Mobile app. In this widget, participants can indicate the consumption of certain food categories. These categories can be configured for each study. By default, the user will see their nutrition entries for the current date, but they can navigate to other dates if desired.

3.3.1 Functional Specification

The food categories and sub-categories are organized in the following tree:

- Fruit & vegetables
 - Fruit
 - Anti-oxidant fruit (berries, grapes)

- Vegetables
- Starchy food (carbohydrates)
 - Potatoes
 - Bread
 - Whole grain bread
 - White bread
 - Rice and grains
 - Rice
 - Grains (oats, barley, rye)
 - Pasta
 - Whole grain pasta
 - White pasta
- Dairy
 - Milk
 - Yogurt
 - Cheese
- Protein food
 - Pulses (beans, peas and lentils)
 - Fish
 - Oil-rich fish
 - White fish & shellfish
 - Eggs
 - Meat
 - White meat
 - Red meat
 - Processed meat
- Fat
 - Oils & spreads
 - Confectionery (aka sugary foods)

The study investigator enables the nutrition widget from the portal app at the study design phase. After enabling it, the investigator configures the nutrition widget by compiling the food categories list offered to the study participant. This is done by selecting any number of food categories and sub-categories from the tree. The tree itself should not be hardcoded, to allow Innovation Sprint personnel to easily expand it with different study needs. To this aim, the tree is maintained in a JSON file (provided alongside this FRS). The JSON tags are as follows:

- Name: The name of the category
- Display: Whether to display the category or not.
- Children: Array of children, possibly empty

The tree is visualised in the portal app. The children should be collapsible to facilitate browsing it. Every branch (not only the top-level leaves) can be selected or not. When a category is selected by the investigator, its display tag is set to true. Each study has its own version of the nutrition tree, with the selections from the investigator.

The study participant uses the nutrition widget to indicate the consumption (if any) of the food categories specified by the study investigator.

The goal of the nutrition widget is to collect the food categories from the list actually consumed each day. When enabled, the widget appears on the mobile app main screen. When opened, it offers the means to select the date, followed by a list of checkboxes, each labelled with the corresponding entry to be displayed from the food categories tree. By default, the widget opens up with the current date selected, but the study participant can navigate to any date. For each date, the list allows the study participant to select and deselect the categories of food they consumed. The quantity is not of interest, the indication of consumption is binary. When navigating to a date, the list indicates any selection that has already been made for that date.

All branches selected by the investigator appear at the participant's mobile app. If the study investigator selects one or more sub-categories of category A, and category A itself, then the sub-categories will be listed first, followed by "Any other A". E.g., if protein food, oil-rich fish, meat and processed meat are selected, then the study participant will be offered the list:

- Processed meat
- Any other meat
- Oil-rich fish
- Any other protein food

3.3.2 Nutrition tree JSON representation

Below the nutrition tree JSON is represented:

```
[{
  "name": "Fruit & vegetables",
  "display": true,
  "children": [{
    "name": "Fruit",
    "display": false,
    "children": [{
      "name": "Anti-oxidant fruit (berries, grapes)",
      "display": true,
      "children": []
    }
  ]
}, {
  "name": "Vegetables",
  "display": false,
  "children": []
}
], {
  "name": "Starchy food (carbohydrates)",
  "display": true,
  "children": [{
    "name": "Potatoes",
    "display": false,
    "children": []
  }, {
    "name": "Bread",
    "display": false,
    "children": [{
      "name": "Whole grain bread",
      "display": true,
      "children": []
    }
  ], {
```

```

        "name": "White bread",
        "display": false,
        "children": []
      }
    ]
  }, {
    "name": "Rice & grains",
    "display": false,
    "children": [{
      "name": "Rice",
      "display": false,
      "children": []
    }, {
      "name": "Grains (oats, barley, rye)",
      "display": true,
      "children": []
    }
  ]
}, {
  "name": "Pasta",
  "display": false,
  "children": [{
    "name": "Whole grain pasta",
    "display": true,
    "children": []
  }, {
    "name": "White pasta",
    "display": false,
    "children": []
  }
]
}
], {
  "name": "Dairy",
  "display": true,
  "children": [{
    "name": "Milk",
    "display": false,
    "children": []
  }, {
    "name": "Yogurt",
    "display": false,
    "children": []
  }, {
    "name": "Cheese",
    "display": false,
    "children": []
  }
]
}, {
  "name": "Protein food",
  "display": true,
  "children": [{
    "name": "Pulses (beans, peas and lentils)",
    "display": true,
    "children": []
  }, {
    "name": "Fish",
    "display": false,
    "children": [{

```

```

        "name": "Oil-rich fish",
        "display": true,
        "children": []
      }, {
        "name": "White fish & shellfish",
        "display": false,
        "children": []
      }
    ]
  }, {
    "name": "Eggs",
    "display": false,
    "children": []
  }, {
    "name": "Meat",
    "display": false,
    "children": [{
      "name": "White meat",
      "display": false,
      "children": []
    }, {
      "name": "Red meat",
      "display": false,
      "children": []
    }, {
      "name": "Processed meat",
      "display": false,
      "children": []
    }
  ]
}
]
}, {
  "name": "Fat",
  "display": true,
  "children": [{
    "name": "Oils & spreads",
    "display": true,
    "children": []
  }, {
    "name": "Confectionery (aka sugary foods)",
    "display": false,
    "children": []
  }
]
}
]

```

As an example, the list created from the given JSON should be:

- Anti-oxidant fruit (berries, grapes)
- Any other fruit & vegetables
- Whole grain bread
- Grains (oats, barley, rye)
- Whole grain pasta
- Any other starchy food (carbohydrates)
- ...

3.3.3 Design

In Figure 7 below we show three screen designs that accompany the specification of the iHelp Nutrition Widget.

Figure 7: Designs for the iHelp Nutrition Widget.

3.3.4 Implementation

The implementation of the nutrition widget is currently in progress and will be described in the follow-up deliverable.

4 Virtual coaching

In this section we will first elaborate on the technical background of virtual coaching (previously ‘conversational coaching’) functionality in the Healthentia platform and mobile app. We will begin with a description of the WOOL Dialogue Platform which is used to author and execute the dialogues. Then, we will discuss the conceptual architecture for the virtual coaching platform - which builds on this technology – and its implementation and roadmap.

4.1 The WOOL Dialogue Platform

The WOOL Dialogue Platform (B., A., H. + 22) is a platform for authoring and execution of scripted dialogues with conversational agents. It was originally developed in the Horizon 2020 Council of Coaches project and released as an open-source project. In May of 2021, the WOOL Foundation was founded to facilitate cooperation between key collaborators, one of which is Innovation Sprint. While the referenced paper provides more details on the platform, in the subsections below we discuss some core aspects to provide an insight.

The WOOL Dialogue Platform is aimed at interdisciplinary teams working on virtual coaching applications in the health domain and consists of three core elements, namely: the dialogue definition language, the dialogue editor, and a set of dialogue execution tools. The underlying philosophy is that the involvement of domain experts is essential in dialogue authoring, but that such authoring but experts should not require extensive technical knowledge of dialogue systems. Therefore, the language and editor were designed to be easy to use and learn, but they still provide powerful features if needed such as the use of variables, conditionals, or custom actions.

4.1.1 The dialogue language

The WOOL dialogue language defines a graph of dialogue steps (or nodes). Each node contains a statement by the agent (or virtual coach) and potential reply options for the user. For example:

```
title: Start
speaker: Robin
position: -416, 112
color: cyan
--
Hello, my name is Robin!

[[Nice to meet you Robin!|NodeRobin1]]
[[Goodbye.|End]]
===
```

This example shows the definition of a single basic node. It has a header, which contains the name of the node, the name of the agent, and some information for its display in the editor (position, color). The body then contains the agent statement and the reply options (between ‘[[‘]]’ characters), which contain the reply the user can give (e.g., ‘Goodbye.’) and the next dialogue step or node that this reply links to (e.g., ‘NodeRobin1’ or ‘End’).

Other features that the language supports are the use of variables – both inclusion and storage – the use of conditionals (if, elseif, else), definition of custom actions (e.g., to influence the user interface), auto-forward replies, input replies (e.g., text or numbers), and linking to other dialogues.

Figure 9: The node editing overlay in the WOOL editor.

The test screen allows authors to test their dialogues in the editor (see Figure 10). This is an important feature, since authoring dialogues is an iterative process and being able to test not just if a dialogue works technically, but also if its flow is good is essential for the resulting dialogue's quality. The dialogue author can switch between the test screen and the dialogue editing screen as desired.

Figure 10: The dialogue test screen in the WOOL editor.

4.1.3 The dialogue execution tools

To execute the WOOL dialogues and incorporate them into virtual coaching applications, the platform includes a set of Java libraries (the WOOL Core). These provide classes to parse the WOOL dialogue scripts, as well as methods for starting and progressing dialogues. They also offer some basic user management.

The Java libraries can be used as part of a custom Java application or incorporated in an Android application. In addition, the platform also offers a web service, which is built around the WOOL Core. If deployed, this web service offers REST API endpoints that provide features such as user authentication, storing and retrieving variables, and starting and progressing dialogues.

4.2 Conceptual architecture of the Virtual Coaching Platform

The Virtual Coaching Platform will consist of both server-side and in-app functionalities. A schematic representation of the conceptual architecture can be found in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Architecture of the virtual coaching platform.

As shown in the conceptual architecture in Figure 11, the higher-level coaching decisions and recommendations are made in the personalised advisor component, while the execution of specific

coaching behaviours such as specific dialogues and notifications will take place in the iHelp Mobile app. The following subsections will zoom in on specific components in this conceptual architecture, while Section 4.4 will elaborate on the first implementation phase.

4.2.1 VC Dialogue Executor

The VC Dialogue Executor is built on the WOOL Web Service that is available in the WOOL Dialogue Platform. It is a Java Spring Boot Application that allows for the functionality within the WOOL Core Library to be deployed as a Web Service. Running this web service requires Java (OpenJDK 16+) and Apache Tomcat (8.5 or 9.0). When deployed, the web service provides endpoints for authentication, data control (e.g., setting variable values) and dialogue execution. Figure 12 shows the Swagger API documentation that becomes available when the service is running.

Figure 12: The Swagger API documentation for the VC Dialogue Executor.

4.2.1.1 Authentication

All calls to the web service API are secured and require a X-Auth-Token. This token should be included in the header of each call. To obtain such a token, a login to a predefined account is required (predefined means configured during the setup of the service). These accounts (username, password and role) can be defined in the users.xml file in the configuration directory of the web service.

To login to the web service the /auth/login/ (POST) end point can be called with the required login parameters or this can be done manually through the Swagger page. The following parameters need to be supplied (with the applicable username and password of course):

```
{
  "password": "p4ssw0rd",
  "tokenExpiration": null,
  "user": "user@example.com"
}
```

When the call has been made, the response should show the HTML 200 status code (successful) and the return message will show the username for which a X-Auth-Token is returned and the token itself:

```
{
  "user": "user@example.com",
  "token": "eyJhbGciOiJIUzUxMiJ9.eyJzdWIiOiJ0ZXN0IiwiaWF0IjoxNjM3MDY4MDk2fQ.62zcI64ZU12piR-73Sn-chbkjblbn9AqXHIic8UFh1S1SMa7p3Aeha_x51rWMLlh6Ch_cYwaiXjv-8enmgX0ag"
}
```

This token can now be included in the header of other calls to the API or can manually be pasted in the authorization field of the Swagger interface.

4.2.1.2 Data control

The data controller provides three end points that can be used to set and get variables from the web service's internal variable store. These are the following:

- /variable (POST)
- /variables (GET)
- /variables (POST)

The two POST end points can be used to set new values for one variable or multiple variables. The GET end point can be used to retrieve the value of one or more variables.

4.2.1.3 Dialogue execution

The dialogue controller contains several end points that can be used to control the dialogue execution. These are the following:

- /dialogue/back-dialogue (POST)
- /dialogue/cancel-dialogue (POST)
- /dialogue/current-dialogue (GET)
- /dialogue/progress-dialogue (POST)
- /dialogue/start-dialogue (POST)

The execution of a WOOL dialogue therefore takes place through a series of API calls. The first one will be a call to start-dialogue which will include the name of a specific dialogue and language. Then the dialogue can be progressed one step by supplying information about the chosen reply option to the progress-dialogue end point. Dialogue progression can also be reversed one step by calling the back-dialogue end point, and execution of a dialogue can be cancelled by calling cancel-dialogue. Furthermore, information about the current dialogue and dialogue step can be obtained by calling current-dialogue.

In a previous version of the web service, it could happen that a user would double-click a button and this could lead to the dialogue skipping a step. Therefore, calls to the back-dialogue and progress-dialogue endpoints now require an identifier to be included so that such duplicate requests will only be executed once.

4.2.2 VC Dialogue Proposal Engine

When it comes to virtual coaching, especially with scripted dialogues, there are multiple levels on which dialogues can be tailored, namely on a domain, topic, action, dialogue act and utterance level (B., A., H. + 22) (also see Figure 13).

Figure 13: Different levels on which coaching conversations can be tailored. Taken with permission from (B., A., H. + 22).

As opposed to having to determine ‘which sentence comes next’ in a broad scope, each of these levels can be seen as a more detailed decision on what should be the next communication towards the user. For example, when you know that the domain for the current conversation is physical activity and you are on the topic of discussing the use of sensors, the interaction between virtual coach and user can be kept within that scope. This helps the dialogue design and authoring process, since authors can then author a set of dialogue scripts that address these more specific topics instead of one large script that covers ‘a dialogue about everything’. The division in domains and topics is often reflected in split into dialogue scripts files. Figure 14 shows a blueprint topic model for health coaching dialogues with conversational agents which can be used to develop a model for a specific coaching domain (B., A., H. + 22). On the other hand, for actions, dialogue acts and utterances the choices are often made within the dialogue scripts by using dialogue language features such as conditionals (if-else statements) and the use of variables within statements, which are then replaced with specific values during dialogue execution.

Figure 14: A blueprint topic model for health coaching dialogues. Taken with permission from (B., A., H. + 22).

When taking a closer look at the topic level, there are two ways in which a topic can be chosen before or during an interaction with a virtual coach. When implemented, these lead to a difference in initiative – that is, either the user or the virtual coach decides the topic of conversation. First, there is the possibility to provide the user with a set of choices in the user interface. For example, a menu-dialogue can be defined, which usually involves the agent making a statement along the lines of ‘how can I help you?’ or ‘what do you want to talk about?’ and the user choosing the topic by selecting one of the answer options that are provided. The second manner involves the system selecting a topic to discuss and starting a corresponding dialogue, which can be implemented in a number of ways. For the interaction this could mean that a dialogue with the virtual coach could start with a statement by the coach such as ‘lets talk about your physical activity’ with which a user can then agree or disagree. A comparison of these two ways of selecting a topic by means of a micro-randomized trial showed that they are equal when it comes to the length of participants’ interactions with the virtual coach (B., A., H. + 22). This comparison study also used a topic structure based on the blueprint model discussed above.

In the virtual coaching platform, both manners of choosing topics will be combined. The VC Dialogue Proposal Engine will be the component that proposes a next dialogue (or topic) that should be executed, but the user will also be offered opportunities to indicate what they want to talk about. The dialogue proposal engine will propose a dialogue using information that is available about the user, such as user profile information, collected data, and identified risks. Earlier implementations of this dialogue proposal engine will involve the use of rules that respond to specific triggers such as the user initiating a conversation or the system identifying the need to send the user a notification or give them specific advice, but we will also investigate the implementation of more intelligent approaches for generating these suggestions.

4.2.3 Virtual Coach UI

As implied by the use of the WOOL dialogue platform, interactions with the virtual coach in the Virtual Coach UI take on the form of chat messages with closed responses (see Figure 15 for an example screenshot). The chat message style is often used for commercial chatbots such as customer support agents on websites, and the use of pre-defined responses is also an often-used interaction style for virtual agents in the health domain.

The virtual coach will be accessible from the main interface of the Healthentia mobile app through the virtual coach icon on the bottom of the screen. Furthermore, the coach will be able to show short statements at the top of the main interface, which can also be used to go to the interaction screen. An example can be seen in Figure 16 below.

Figure 15: An example screenshot of chat UI in the Healthentia mobile app.

Figure 16: An example message from the virtual coach on the main interface.

4.3 Using the VC Architecture for Personalized Content Delivery

The preceding sections discuss components and potential principles for delivering personalised content. Taking into account these components and the design of personalisation prevention and intervention measures described in Deliverable 5.4, in this subsection we will provide some examples of what personalised content delivery could look like in iHelp.

First, to be able to personalise content to a user, information about that user should be collected. Relevant user characteristics are for example age, gender, goal orientation (promotion or prevention), health literacy, whether someone smokes or not, if a user has a chronic condition, if a user has a disability, and if a user is pregnant/postpartum. It can also include a response to a question about the level of users' conscious efforts for healthy behaviour in the domains of physical activity, nutrition, sleep, and stress (reduction), which could be never, rarely, about half of the time, most of the time, or daily. This information could be collected through an intake questionnaire or within an intake dialogue with a coach.

Once the user characteristics are known, a risk assessment could be performed within the iHelp platform. This assessment can then lead to recommendations on various domains (e.g., suitable changes to physical

activity or diet). When related to the literature described above, these recommendations can be seen as indicators for which domains are important for coaching and what the high level goals within these domains could be (e.g., eating less sugar).

The VC Dialogue Proposal Engine could then within the domain, e.g., physical activity, coach the user towards their high-level goal (e.g., increasing the number of active minutes per week). It could, for example, first propose a dialogue on the topic of setting a more specific short-term goal, followed by a dialogue to discuss actions to achieve that goal.

As a final step, within these dialogues, the content could be adjusted to the user by using conditionals and variables. Or, if dialogues are significantly different for certain user characteristics, that is, instead of just different dialogue acts and utterances they would need different actions, different dialogues could be written. For example, dialogue content could be different when the content is delivered to a promotion-oriented user as opposed to when it is delivered to a prevention-oriented user, for people with different levels of literacy, for active versus non-active users, or even for a combination of characteristics. To give a short example:

For a prevention-oriented user: *“Did you know that even some small changes to your lifestyle (e.g., walking or avoiding certain foods) can help you to avoid various diseases and could enable you to enjoy longevity and fuller mobility for longer? Should we see how I can help you to introduce those changes?”*

For a promotion-oriented user: *“Did you know that even some small changes to your lifestyle (e.g., walking or avoiding certain foods) can help you to improve your health and enable you to enjoy longevity and fuller mobility for longer? Should we see how I can help you to introduce those changes?”*

4.4 Virtual Coaching Implementation Phase 1

The Virtual Coach is implemented following a client-server paradigm where the client is the Healthentia Mobile application, and the server a specific module in the Healthentia back-end server. Dialogues are stored and executed on the server component (VC Web Service), and the client is charged with (a) rendering each step of the dialogue and (b) communicating the user’s reply options back to the server. Specifically, the client is built using an embedded web-viewer inside the Healthentia ReactNative app.

The deployment view of the client-server-based virtual coaching subcomponent is shown in Figure 17 below.

Figure 17: Deployment view of the client-server-based virtual coaching subcomponent.

Figure 17 contains labels of the 5 major steps needed to process a user's request to view the virtual coach in the mobile application. These five steps are explained shortly below:

1. The "VC Module" – a logical component of the Healthentia Mobile app – is triggered by the user tapping on the "virtual coach" icon in the bottom menu bar of the app. The VC Module calls an end-point in the main Healthentia Service and passes along the Healthentia Authentication Token.
2. The endpoint is served by the VC Web UI Service, a .net Razer Page implementation that uses the Healthentia Authentication token to retrieve a number of relevant subject details from the Healthentia DB: the subjectID, the trialId, and the currently used language of the user that made the request.
3. Next, the VC Web UI Service performs a login (using an admin-account) to the VC Web Service (our local WOOL Web Service deployment). The login is done using an "admin" account that has access to start/progress/cancel/etc. features for every possible Healthentia user – i.e. it results in a kind of API Token, the VC Auth Token.
4. With the information collected (subjectId, trialId, language, and vc-auth-token), the VC Web UI Service generates HTML/CSS/JS page that is served to the mobile client.
5. The now locally running (on the phone) web page will handle the step-by-step execution of dialogue through the VC Web Service.

This process is further detailed in the sequence diagram as show in Figure 18 below.

Figure 18: Sequence Diagram for the process of running a dialogue in the Healthentia Mobile application - Virtual Coach user interface.

Figure 19 below shows the architecture behind the process of triggering a virtual coaching dialogue. The Embedded Dialogue Editor (right-side) as part of the Healthentia Web Portal is used to author a dialogue script. This dialogue script is stored in the Dialogue Storage Service. The Healthentia Mobile App (top-left) can be used to start a conversation with the Virtual Coach. The user is presented with the Embedded Virtual Coach UI that is served by the Virtual Coach UI Render Service (a web server that serves an HTML page). The Render Service talks to the Dialogue Execution Service to do a step-by-step execution of the dialogue that was authored using the Embedded Dialogue Editor. Finally, the Dialogue Knowledge Base Bridge Service ensures that information about the relevant Subjects that is available in the Healthentia Platform is also available within the dialogues.

Figure 19: High level component view of the process of triggering a Virtual Coach Dialogue from the Healthentia Portal on the Mobile App.

4.5 Virtual Coaching Roadmap

The implementation of virtual coaching for iHelp in Healthentia follows a roadmap that is included as Figure 20 below. While it is not set in stone that all steps will be implemented within the scope of the project, this roadmap provides an overview of the envisioned virtual coaching components and functionalities.

Healthentia Virtual Coaching Technology Roadmap

Figure 20: The virtual coaching roadmap.

5 Clinical pathway modelling

The various delivery mechanisms provide the communication between the iHelp platform and the user. However, not all types of communication and content are applicable for all users or for all stages in their health process. The Clinical Pathway Modelling Tool can be used to define a “clinical pathway” – a set of relevant states and transitions that participants in the iHelp platform go through. Such states can, for example, represent a set of user characteristics or parameters with specific values, or steps in a treatment protocol. Each of these states then has specific actions attached to it. In the following paragraphs, we will describe the specifications for clinical pathway modelling as it will be implemented in the Healthentia platform.

Just as the WOOL Editor allows healthcare professionals to author their own dialogue content for the virtual embodied conversational agent – effectively giving great control over the content being delivered – similarly, the clinical pathway tool is used to give control to the healthcare professional regarding the overall path and trajectory of the treatment or study.

The clinical pathway tool is currently being implemented as part of the virtual coaching suite of tools. Below we describe its functional specifications that are used to develop the tool.

5.1 Functional Specifications

Pathway

A Clinical **Pathway** is the means to execute **Actions** based on the **States** the different **Subjects** are in and the **Transitions** between these **States**. Thus, a Clinical **Pathway** defines a flow between a series of **States**, as governed by the **Transition** between them, resulting to **Actions** performed.

Each **Subject** in a **Study** may be assigned to one (or multiple) **Pathways**.

A Pathway is defined by the following properties:

- A **Pathway** has a set of **States**.
- A **Pathway** has a set of **Transitions** (between those **States**).

State

A **State** represents the situation a subject is found at any given time. It can refer to a collection of clinical outcomes (e.g. the health states in cancer disease progression) or simply a step in some clinical protocol that is strictly determined by the passage of days.

- Each **State** has a unique identifier.
- One of the **States** in a **Pathway** must be identified as the default/start **State**.
- Each **State** has a name that may be defined by the user.
- The first time a **Subject** is assigned to a **Pathway** he/she starts at a specific **State** that is marked as the “default/start” **State**, unless specified otherwise.
- Each triplet of **Subject** – **Pathway** – **State** is stored.
- Each **Subject** can move between **States** as defined by the **Transitions**.
- Each **State** can have a set of **Actions** associated to it.

Transition

A **Transition** connects a *source State* with a *target State* and defines the direction from Source to Target.

A Transition has the following properties:

- **Transition id:** a **Transition** has a identifier, unique within the given **Pathway**.
- **source State:** The identifier of the source **State**.
- **target State:** The identifier of the target **State**.
- **Rules:** A **Transition** can have 1 or multiple **Rules** associated with it. A **Rule** defines a **Trigger**, a set of **Conditions**, and an optional set of **Actions**. When the **Trigger** and **Conditions** are met, the **Transition** is fired, moving the **Subject** from source to target **State**.

Rules

A Rule is associated with a transition and defines when (Trigger) and under which conditions (Conditions) the transition should occur. Optionally, it can also define which additional Actions should occur immediately (other than “executing” the transition itself – moving the subject from source to target state). A Rule has the following properties:

- **Triggers:** A Rule can define 1 or many Triggers. A Trigger defines an event. When any of the defined trigger events occur, the Rule’s conditions are evaluated to see if the Rule can be fired.
- **Conditions:** A Rule can define 1 or many Conditions. All conditions are evaluated when one of the Trigger events take place. If all conditions defined in a Rule evaluate to true the rule is fired, and the Transition associated with this Rule will take place, as well as any optional other Actions defined.
- **Actions:** A Rule can define 0 or many Actions (see §0) that will be executed immediately when the rule is fired (i.e. before the transition takes place).

As an example, **Conditions** may be defined using the following type of information:

- Questionnaire scores or answers of specific questions (e.g., “The outcome score of Questionnaire SCHMIDT_MENTAL_HEALTH_SCALE is less than or equal to 25”).
- Profile attributes, such as the Subject’s gender, or age (e.g., “The age of the Subject is between 65 and 80”).
- Measurements from devices such as step counts or sleep duration (e.g., “The average number of steps of the Subject over the past 7 days is more than 8000”).
- Tags, which are similar to profile attributes (e.g., “Subject has tag ‘diabetes’”).

As an example, **Triggers** may be defined using the following type of information:

- A new measurement of parameter X is available.
- A new instance of Questionnaire X has been answered.
- It’s 20:00.

Actions

Actions are executed by the pathway.

- An **Action** is attached to a specific **State** or **Transition**.
- An **Action** attached to a state has a time schedule attached to it, e.g.:
 - Every Monday at 07:30 PM.
 - Once on the 3rd of May, 2022.

- Now.
- Etc...
- An **Action** attached to a transition is executed when the transition occurs.
- An **Action** has a specific “body” (the “action” part of the **Action**), which can be any type of operation supported by the Healthentia platform. The list of available **Actions**, in order of importance is as follows:
 1. Send a questionnaire (currently supported)
 2. Apply a tag (currently supported)
 3. Send a notification (currently supported)
 4. Send a message (currently supported)
 5. Schedule a Teleconsultation (currently supported)
 6. Generate alert (currently supported)
 7. Enable/disable module (to be implemented)
 8. Trigger Virtual Coach messages (to be implemented)
 9. Enable / Disable Virtual Coach topics (to be implemented)
 10. Apply a Rule (to be implemented)

5.1.1 The Class Diagram

The definitions of concepts as defined in Section 5.1 could be modeled in a class diagram as shown in Figure 21 below.

Figure 21: Class Diagram of the concepts related to the Pathway.

5.1.2 Use case

As a screening procedure for general cancer risk, the Hospital of East Fictional Town wants to run a large population-based study, monitoring the general health of the general population in the city. Every day they want to ask all study participants about their “daily health” using the following questionnaire (Q_DAILY_HEALTH):

Q: How do you feel about your health today?

- Very Negative (Score: -2)
- Negative (Score: -1)
- Neutral (Score: 0)
- Positive (Score: +1)
- Very Positive (Score: +2)

As long as Subjects answer “Neutral”, “Positive”, or “Very Positive”, nothing special happens. However, when a Subject answers “Negative” or “Very Negative”, we consider them to be “At Risk” and want to know more (i.e., immediately answer the “Positive Health Questionnaire” (Q_POS_HEALTH)). When the subject on the next day again answers Negative or Very Negative on the Q_DAILY_HEALTH, we consider those subjects to be “Sick” and we additionally want them to answer the EQ5D5L questionnaire (Q_EQ5D5L), and want to enable Subjects to report various Symptoms. At any moment, when Subjects answer “Positive” or “Very Positive” on the Q_DAILY_HEALTH questionnaire, they will be considered “Healthy” again (the default starting state for each Subject).

This use case can be represented by the Clinical Pathway sketch as shown in Figure 22 below. Note that the Action “Send Q_POS_HEALTH Immediately” that are attached to the Transitions (between A->B, and between B->C) could also have been attached to the States (B and C).

Figure 22: Clinical Pathway for the fictional “Daily Health Monitoring” use case.

5.2 Implementation

Implementation of the Clinical Pathway Tool is currently in progress and will be described in the follow-up deliverable.

6 Conclusions

This document summarises the developments carried out in the scope of T5.3 (“Delivery Mechanisms for Personalised Healthcare and Real-time Feedback”) of the project for delivering the user-centric smart application to support the delivery of personalized healthcare. As such, it will be based on Healthentia Healthentia Mobile app, while highlighting the features that will be (further) developed in the context of the iHelp project to cover the scenarios and needs of clinicians, as identified by the user requirements (D2.1) of the project. Moreover, three categories of common types of delivery mechanisms were identified. These were the (i) Data visualisation; (ii) Feedback messages and nudges; and (iii) Conversational coaching. To this end, in this deliverable we describe the visualisation of collected data in the Healthentia mobile app, as well as the initial design and specifications of the WOOL Dialogue Platform. The latter will act as the main platform for authoring and execution of scripted dialogues with conversational agents. Finally, we introduce the Clinical Pathway Modelling Tool, which is a set of relevant states and transitions that participants in the iHelp platform go through.

This is the first iteration of two documents that are planned to be released through the project. This first version establishes the baseline for the design and implementation of delivery mechanisms for personalised healthcare and real-time feedback within the iHelp project. While next iteration will focus on the integration activities and on the runtime, this one focuses on the design, the specifications, and the initial user interfaces, as have been identified until M16 of the project.

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List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CA	Consortium Agreement
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EHRs	Electronic Health Records
EQ-5D-5L	Self-assessed, health related, quality of life questionnaire
EU	European Union
HHRs	Holistic Health Records
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
M	Month
REST	Representational State Transfer
RWD	Real World Data
T	Task
UI	User Interface